

Talking Stick Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Class V Respiration UPTD SDN 124385 Pematangsiantar

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ABSTRACT

The background to this research is based on activities carried out by researchers in class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar, namely the teacher still uses conventional learning models so that students are less active in the learning process. This causes the learning process to be less than optimal and student learning outcomes have not been achieved in accordance with the Minimum Completeness Criteria. From this problem, it is necessary to find a solution, namely by implementing the *Talking Stick learning model*. This learning model is suitable to be applied to thematic learning because this learning model invites students to be more active and can train students' mentality and courage in providing their own opinions. This learning model can improve the quality of thematic learning and also influence student learning outcomes. This type of research uses a *pre-experimental method* with a research design using a *one group pretest-posttest design* with a sample of 25 students. Based on the results of the data analysis tests carried out, the hypothesis test results obtained were $t_{count} = 11.658$ and $t_{table} = 2.064$ with $t_{count} > t_{table} = 11.658 > 2.064$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. With this explanation, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Talking Stick learning mode* on student learning outcomes in subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for breathing in class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Education is very important for improving human resources. Because education is the most important thing in the maturation process of every human being which influences the development of students' potential, so that sharing of very useful skills is formed through teaching and training efforts carried out by facilitating activities in the teaching and learning process.

Learning is the process of changing a person's behavior towards positive things. Learning can broaden a person's insight and bring change to the individual. Learning is not only about knowledge, but learning can also take the form of skills, interests, character and adjustment to society, nation and state.

Learning is a process of interaction between educators and students carried out at school. According to Robiyanto (2021:115) states that learning is an effort or endeavor of an educator, to help students learn easily. This learning is also combined in learning components that interact and integrate with each other. However, what is happening now is that students still do not understand the learning material. By overcoming this problem, there will definitely be cooperation between teachers, where educators can prepare models and use teaching materials that are appropriate to the learning material being carried out. In order to achieve these learning objectives, educators can implement a new paradigm, namely using an innovative learning model. One innovative model is *the Talking Stick learning mode*.

Talking Stick learning model is one of the models used by teachers in implementing learning, where this learning model is learning that is carried out using sticks. According to Huda Miftahul (2014: 224), the *Talking Stick* learning mode is a model used by Native Americans to invite everyone to talk or express opinions in a forum (inter-tribal meeting). This learning mode is used to determine the influence of student learning outcomes on learning.

Student learning outcomes are changes that occur at the cognitive, affective and psychomotor levels. Learning outcomes are achievements achieved by students academically through exams and all assignments given, students' activeness in asking and answering questions that supports all learning outcomes according to Dakhi Agustin (2020:468). By looking at the influence of the *Talking Stick* learning model on student learning outcomes, this model can be used in learning in fifth grade elementary school. Therefore, this research aims to determine the effect of the *Talking Stick learning model* on student learning outcomes.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

In carrying out research activities, the theoretical framework contains theories related to the research title regarding Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in class V. This theory is the basis and reference for the description of the things to be researched. Students can be expected to be braver in expressing their own opinions so that student learning outcomes are better. This conceptual framework can be depicted in the concept map below:

METHOD

The type of research used is experimentation with a quantitative approach. Arikunto (2018:9) states that experimentation is one of the methods used to look for a causal relationship (casual relationship) between two factors that are deliberately created by researchers by eliminating or reducing other disturbing factors. The type of research carried out was the *Pre-Experimental Design method*, with a research design using a *One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design*. The population in this research is all class V students consisting of 25 students in one class and the sample for this research is 25 students. The instrument in this research is a test instrument. The instruments in this research are test questions which are tested using validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differential power tests. Other data is collected through documentation results. Then the data results were analyzed using hypothesis testing using the *paired samples test analysis technique*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted to find out whether there was an influence from a treatment, namely the *Talking Stick Learning Model*, carried out by researchers on student learning outcomes for Theme 2 Subtheme 2 learning 1 and 2 in class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar. The subjects in this research are class V. The lessons delivered by researchers in conducting experiments during the research are Theme 2 Clean Air for Health Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration lessons 1 and 2. Where, each lesson contains learning points. However, before carrying out the research, the first step taken by the researcher was to test the test instrument. From the instrument test carried out, results were obtained where of the 35 questions tested there were 25 questions that were included in the valid category and 10 questions that were invalid. Next, a reliability test was carried out, the result obtained was 0.902, so the data was considered reliable. Then, a difficulty level test was carried out, consisting of 10 easy questions, 14 medium questions and 1 difficult question. Then, for the last one, a different power test was carried out where 13 good questions were obtained, 9 good questions, and 3 bad questions. After completing the research instrument test, the data analysis continued. There are 25 questions that are declared valid and will be used during the *pretest* and *posttest* when conducting research.

The learning implementation carried out by the researcher began with conducting a *pretest* to determine the students' initial abilities. Then the students' pretest answers were analyzed by the researcher. After that, the researcher carried out

teaching and learning process activities using the *Talking Stick learning model treatment* using learning from the book Theme 2 Clean Air for Health, Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in lessons 1 and 2. After being given the treatment, the researcher continued by giving a *posttest* with the following questions. the same as the pretest to determine student learning outcomes after using the *Talking Stick learning mode*. The results of the pretest data analysis carried out were that the average student learning outcome was 63.68 with the highest score being 88 and the lowest score being 52. In the *posttest* the average student learning outcome was 87.2 with the highest score being 96 and the lowest score being 72.

First, a data normality test is carried out, where the normality test is used to determine whether the collected research data is normal or not. This normality test uses SPSS 21 with a significance level > 0.05 , the pretest normality test obtained 0.158 the data is said to be normal because $0.158 > 0.05$ then the data is said to be normal. After carrying out the normality test, a homogeneity test is then carried out, where this homogeneity test is carried out to determine whether the research data collected according to the specified criteria is homogeneous or not, significance > 0.05 , the significance value is 0.132, so it is said that the data is homogeneous because $0.132 > 0.05$. Next, an N-Gain score test is carried out, where the N-Gain test is used to determine the effect of learning outcomes before and after learning in the specified category. So an N-Gain value of 0.63 is obtained in the medium category, so it can be said that there is an influence on student learning outcomes. After carrying out the N-Gain test, continue with hypothesis testing. Based on hypothesis testing where the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $11.658 > 2.064$ and/or significant $0.00 < 0.05$.

Table 1. Hasil Uji t

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	posttes t - pretest	23.520	10.088	2.018	19.356	27.684	11.658	24	.000

Based on table 1 above, it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an influence of the *Talking Stick Learning Model* on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Clean Air for Health, Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in Class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers in class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar, it can be concluded that it can be seen from data analysis and discussion using the t test applied to the hypothesis, stating that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus it is concluded that there is an influence of the *Talking Stick Learning*

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REFERENCES

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2018. *Research Procedures*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- Asyafah, A. (2019). *Considering Learning Models (Theoretical-Critical Study of Learning Models in Islamic Education)*. Journal of Islamic Education. Vol 6(1): p. 19-32.
- Dakhi, AS 2020. *Improving Student Learning Outcomes*. Journal of Education and development. Vol 8(2): p. 468-470.
- Fajrin, OA (2018). *The Influence of the Talking Stick Model on Elementary School Students' Social Studies Learning Outcomes*. Journal of Basic Education. Vol 2(1A). pp: 85-91.
- Fauhah, H. and Brillian, R. 2021. *Analysis of the Make A Match Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes*. Journal of Office Administration Education. Vol 9(2): p. 321-334.
- Huda, M. 2014. *Teaching and Learning Models*. Yogyakarta: Learning Library
- Imas & Berlin. 2016. *Various Development of Learning Models to Improve Teacher Professionalism*. Jakarta: Pena said
- Istarani. 2011. *58 Innovative Learning Models*. Medan: Media Persada
- Lestari, NK T, et al. (2018). *The Influence of the Talking Stick Learning Model Assisted with Regional Songs on Social Studies Learning Outcomes* . Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation. Vol 1(4): p. 290-297.
- Pulungan, I., & I. 2016. *ENCYCLOPEDIA OF EDUCATION* . Medan: Larispa
- Rahayu, R., & M. Djazari. (2016). *Analysis of the Quality of National Pre-Exam Questions in Economics and Accounting Subjects*. Indonesian Journal of Accounting Education. Vol. XIV(1).
- Rahmadhani, R. and Abdiyah, A. 2020. *Effectiveness of Using Basic Mathematics Modules in Number Material on Learning Outcomes* . Journal of the Mathematics Education Study Program. Vol9(1): p. 64-71.
- Robiyanto, A. (2021). *The Influence of the Problem Based Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes*. Journal of Elementary School Teacher Education. Vol 2(1): p. 114-121.
- Saragih, LM, Darinda, ST, & Dewi, A. (2021). *The Influence of the Open Ended Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Thematic Learning*. BASICEDU JOURNAL . Vol 5(4): p. 2644-2652.

Setiawan, Eko. 2018. *Theoretical & Practical Thematic Learning*. Jakarta: Erlangga

Sugiyono. 2019. *Educational Research Methods (Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Approaches)*. Bandung: ALFABETA

Tati, ADR, et al. (2022). The Influence of the Talking Stick Learning Model on the Learning Outcomes of Grade IV Elementary School Students in Science Subjects. *Scientific Journal of Basic Education*. Vol 7(2): p. 302-308.

Utama, IGMP, Ketut, D. Tanggu, R. (2019). *The Influence of the Talking Stick Model on Civics Learning Outcomes in Class V Semester II Elementary School Students in Cluster I, Gerokgak District, Academic Year 2017/2018*. *Journal of Pedagogy and Learning*. Vol 2(1): p. 123-130.

Utami, SG, et al. (2020). *The Influence of the Talking Stick Type Cooperative Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Class V Thematic Learning in Bengkulu City State Elementary Schools* . *Journal of Basic Education Research*. Vol 3(2): p. 162-170.

Wati, E. et al. (2022). *Analysis of Student Character in Science Subjects in Elementary Schools* . *BASICEDU JOURNAL*. Vol 6(4): p. 5994-6004.